

The preservation of know-how in Peruvian companies: An exploratory analysis of knowledge management practices

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Abstract

Business know-how is a key intangible asset for competitive advantage, productivity, and innovation within organizations; Knowledge Management (KM) serves as the steward of business know-how by identifying, capturing, sharing, and creating knowledge. However, in the Peruvian industry, there are very few studies showing the extent of care and KM in companies. This study analyzes the current situation of KM in Peruvian companies through a quantitative approach using a descriptive method that employs surveys directed at workers within the Peruvian industry. The objectives of this study are to determine the extent of implementation of KM models, the challenges to their implementation, and the benefits that KM provides to the Peruvian industry. Additionally, a general diagnosis of the Peruvian industry will be elaborated. The results show that only 16% of respondents indicate that the company they work for has implemented a formal KM model. Furthermore, the challenges for implementation stem from the lack of consideration of KM in the strategic plan, unfamiliarity with theoretical KM models, the absence of dedicated roles for KM, and the lack of budget allocated to KM. On the other hand, the data shows that companies that apply KM strategies obtain the following benefits: a significant increase in the culture of knowledge sharing, greater use of technology for knowledge transmission, and more reliance on prior knowledge in decision-making.

Keywords: know-how, knowledge management, Peruvian industry, intellectual asset

Introduction

Business know-how is defined as the collection of unique knowledge, skills, experiences, techniques, and procedures that an organization has accumulated over time. It is practical and efficient knowledge for the organization, an intangible asset that cannot be easily patented but provides a significant competitive advantage (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). This know-how enables the development of innovative products and services, the improvement of production processes, and the establishment of lasting relationships with customers. Knowledge Management (KM) acts as the steward of business know-how by identifying, capturing, sharing, and creating knowledge, ensuring that the company's intellectual capital remains alive, develops, and is maximally utilized (Grant, 1996).

Various international studies have demonstrated the benefits of Knowledge Management (KM) in terms of safeguarding know-how that generates innovation, efficiency, and value creation, allowing companies to respond proactively to market changes. Despite these findings, in the

case of Peruvian industry, there are significant gaps in the literature regarding how these practices are implemented in the local industry and what barriers companies face in integrating KM into their organizational culture and operational strategies.

This study seeks to provide an exploratory analysis of know-how preservation in the Peruvian industry through the implementation of knowledge management strategies. Utilizing a quantitative approach and a descriptive methodology, and employing surveys directed at collaborators in the Peruvian industry, this work identifies the knowledge and implementation levels of the principal KM models, evaluates the value of KM within the Peruvian industry, and examines the organizational factors that limit its adoption as well as the benefits observed where it has been implemented.

The results show a low level of a knowledge management model adoption. This situation is due to the lack of KM strategies aligned with the company's strategic plan, a lack of familiarity with KM models, and a scarcity of dedicated roles for this practice, which has reduced the effective development of know-how management in the local context.

Finally, it is observed that in those companies that have implemented a KM model, a culture of knowledge exchange among their members is fostered. Additionally, an alignment is established between the incentives offered, especially those of an intrinsic and transcendent nature, and the participation of members in KM strategies. Lastly, a more intense use of technological tools is observed.

Literature review

Literature shows diverse definitions about knowledge management. Wiig (1997), for example, defines KM as systematic, explicit and deliberated construct; the renewal and application of knowledge to maximize the efficiency and utility of a company's knowledge in relation to its knowledge assets. Additionally, Maier (2007) defines it as the regular function responsible for the management, selection, implementation, and evaluation of strategies aimed at objectives that seek to improve the way internal and external knowledge is managed in order to enhance the company's performance.

Knowledge Management is a factor that could determine success in an organization. A highly uncertain and dynamic environment places importance on the ability of the company's members to capture, learn, and transfer knowledge, rather than focusing on complementary factors (i.e., company size, organizational hierarchy, and physical resources) (Porter, 1991).

The maintenance and competitiveness of a company depend on the creation, transfer, and application of knowledge (Grant, 1996) (Deed & Decarlis, 1999). In this sense, innovation becomes essential to compete in a creative economy. Consequently, agile tools, information technology, and management are also required to guide and support the company's members (Ribiere & Doug, 2010).

The effective implementation of Knowledge Management processes becomes a key strategy for improving the company's performance (Wong & Aspinwall, 2004), as well as for fostering and cultivating the individual knowledge of the company's members, with the aim of developing continuous organizational learning (Kongpichayanond, 2009). In this regard, customer knowledge, product excellence, and process improvement are ways in which Knowledge Management can add value to a company (O'Dell & Grayson, 1998).

Empirical studies have shown that the implementation of Knowledge Management processes has a positive correlation with the company's performance. It has been demonstrated that some companies can develop higher-quality products and services at a lower cost through process innovation (Ofek & Sarvary, 2001).

Additionally, some organizations with highly mature Knowledge Management strategies showed double the benefits compared to those with low maturity levels (Hubert, 2011). Other studies have found similar evidence establishing a strong relationship between Knowledge Management, performance, and benefits (Yang, 2010) (López-Nicolás & Meroño-Cerdán, 2011) (Rasula, Vuksic & Sremberger, 2012) (Chen & Huang, 2009).

Know-how preservation implies systematic processes that are integrated into what is called a Knowledge Management model, which coordinates the activities of acquisition, creation, storage, and communication of knowledge by individuals and groups.

There are various KM models that vary based on the approach, application, and interpretation of the processes of generation, storage, and dissemination of knowledge. Among these models, the following stand out: the Organizational Epistemology Model by Von Krogh and Ross (1995), Nonaka and Takeuchi's Knowledge Spiral (1995), Choo's Knowledge Management – Making Sense (2006), Wiig's model to Build and Use Knowledge (Wiig, 1994), Boisot's Information Space (1999), and the Complex Adaptive Intelligent System (ICAS) (Beer, 1981; Bennet and Bennet, 2004).

These models are theoretical. However, Handzic & Hasan (2003) did an effort to convert those models into a one that is more practical. Following Handzic & Hasan (2003) effort, Zocón (2024) articulates a framework divided in 5 dimensions and 17 components that are unified and based in a humanistic model for people management. This last model is presented to analyze and be implemented in Peruvian industry.

Given the importance of implementing Knowledge Management in a company to protect its know-how, it is crucial to evaluate its application in Peruvian companies to analyze their sustainability and competitiveness.

Methodology

The exploratory analysis was conducted with a convenience sample, defining the population as all employees of Peruvian companies. The data collection method included the use of surveys that were sent via email to all graduates of the PAD School of Management at the University of Piura and to the professional networks of the research team.

The survey questions were formulated based on a list of components derived from the analysis of the key Knowledge Management models previously mentioned. This survey was validated by experts and then tested with three individuals from companies in different sectors and with diverse roles. After these pilot interviews, the necessary corrections were made, and the survey was reviewed again by three experts.

The survey contained 58 questions, several of which are Likert scale type, rated from 1 to 5, with 1 being very low and 5 being very high. Table 1 presents the components of the KM models considered in the research and their definitions.

Table 1: Components of KM models

Component	Subcomponent	Definition
Human	Culture	Identify the need of a KM culture to generate and transform knowledge among workers, and create innovation.
	Person	Considers fundamental the relationship between knowledge and the workers that acquire knowledge and use it.
Conversion cycle		Stablish a defined cycle to transform: 1) knowledge within the firm, 2) the worker evolution inside and outside the firm, and 3) the type of knowledge (personal, shared, public)
Decision- taking process		Define the processes to use knowledge to take decisions
Organization process		Stablish the process and requirements that allow the management of knowledge conversion cycles, knowledge storage, selection, connectivity, codification, abstraction and the purpose of it
Categorization		Stablish the types of knowledge by its state (personal, shared, public) and kind (factual, conceptual, expectative-based, methodological)
Knowledge communities		Stablish the need and process definition for the creation and direction of knowledge communities
Knowledge networks		Stablish the need and process definition for the creation and direction of knowledge networks

Source: Zocón (2024)

To avoid bias from the managers leading the organizations and to protect confidentiality, the study population was defined as the workers in the Peruvian industry. This allowed for the inclusion of data from different organizational levels, the possibility of having a larger sample, greater reach, and the ability to conduct the study more quickly.

Sample heterogeneity was assessed using the Blaux index for contextual variables based on the type of company and certain characteristics of the respondents (Table 2).

Table 2: Blaux Index

Variable	Blaux Index
Firm's sector	0.91
Firm's classification (big, medium or small size)	0.77
Origin of the company (Peruvian, foreign subsidiary managed from abroad, autonomous Peruvian belonging to a foreign group)	0.46
Number of workers	0.79

Variable	Blaux Index
Firm's benefits range	0.83
Years working	0.74
Worker's Area	0.91
Job position	0.85

Heterogeneity was observed in all variables except for the origin of the company, because most companies are of Peruvian origin. In this regard, 70% of the respondents belonged to a company of Peruvian origin; 17% to a Peruvian company that is part of a foreign group; and 13% to a foreign subsidiary managed from abroad.

Regarding the revenue level of the companies (Figure 1), heterogeneity was observed in the sample, but there was a slight concentration in the revenue level exceeding 100 million dollars.

Figure 1: Distribution of the sample categorized by revenue

Figure 2 shows the percentage of working area of the collaborator

Figure 2: Distribution of the sample by working area

To conduct the general diagnosis of knowledge management (KM) in the Peruvian industry, Zocón's Systemic Knowledge Management Model (MSGC) (2024) was used, which analyzes five dimensions: 1. Strategy and Direction, 2. Human, 3. Knowledge Management Processes, 4. Technology, 5. Indicators. Each dimension was evaluated on a scale from 1 to 5, and the evaluation process consisted of three steps. Table 3 presents the evaluation process.

Table 3: Methodology for a KM general diagnosis

Methodology Steps	Definition
Mapping of Questions and Alignment to the MSGC	Determine the questions corresponding to each dimension.
Normalization	Transform the scale of the questions to achieve a standardized measurement using a linear model on a scale from 1 to 5.
Weighted Sum of Results	Assign a weight to each question and sum the results of each question by dimension, then divide the total by the number of questions

Results

The results have been organized into four categories: the degree of implementation of knowledge management (KM) models; the challenges companies face for proper implementation; the benefits gained by companies that implement a KM model; and a general and synthetic diagnosis of Peruvian companies based on the components of Zocón's model (2024).

Degree of Implementation of KM Models

There is a strong awareness and high valuation of the importance of KM. This is reflected in the fact that 80.2% of respondents consider KM to be important or very important (sum of 4 and 5 on the Likert scale) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Valuation of the importance of KM

A total of 15.5% of respondents indicate that their organizations implement a Knowledge Management (KM) model (Figure 4), while 34.3% state that it is applied partially. Conversely, the remaining 50.1% believes that it is not applied or is unaware of its existence. This highlights the limited dissemination of the KM strategy within organizations and the low application of KM models in these settings.

Figure 4: Application of a KM model

Challenges for the Implementation of KM

Only 18.0% of respondents reported having a good or high level of information (sum of 4 and 5 on the Likert scale) regarding Knowledge Management (KM) models (Figure 5). This finding suggests that a lack of knowledge is a significant factor limiting the implementation of KM strategies

Figure 5: Knowledge of KM models

Approximately 53.5% of respondents indicate that they do not have or are unsure whether their organization has considered Knowledge Management (KM) in its strategic plan (Figure 6). This is a significant indicator of the non-inclusion or lack of communication regarding the KM strategy.

Figure 6: KM in the strategic plan

In addition, only 25.2% of respondents indicate that their organizations have formal positions and roles for Knowledge Management (KM) (Figure 7). This suggests that there might not be an individual responsible for the KM strategy, which could lead to isolated initiatives that are not systematized and not connected to other strategies of the company.

Figure 7: Unique roles for KM

Approximately 28.3% of respondents indicated (Figure 8) that the Human Management area is responsible for managing the Knowledge Management (KM) strategy, suggesting a tendency to approach KM solely from a human development perspective, possibly limiting it to training and learning programs, which are prevalent in Human Management. This indicates that it is not managed under a systemic model that encompasses all dimensions of KM.

Figure 8: Responsible for KM implementation

It was also highlighted that 27.4% believe that no area is responsible for the Knowledge Management (KM) strategy. Therefore, it can be deduced that the organization lacks the capacity to implement coherent KM strategies. Finally, another challenge for implementing a KM model is that only 23.4% state that the organization has a budget for KM (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Existence of Budget for KM

Benefits of Implementing KM

Employees in companies that integrate a Knowledge Management (KM) model actively share their knowledge with their coworkers 63.3% more than those in companies without a KM model. Additionally, collaborators receive 56.3% more intrinsic incentives. Regarding transcendental incentives, collaborators gain 28.8% more of these incentives. Furthermore, employees report that past information is used for decision-making 41% more often. Lastly, in their organizations, they make more intensive use of technology, with an increase of 57.7% (Figure 10)

Figure 10: KM Benefits

Discussion

According to previous studies, companies with higher maturity in their Knowledge Management (KM) strategies demonstrated twice the benefits compared to those with low maturity (Hubert, 2011). Although this study did not assess the impact of implementing a KM model on economic benefits, other advantages have been identified that enhance organizational efficiency, potentially leading to reduced costs and increased revenues. These benefits include: the use of prior knowledge in decision-making; better alignment of intrinsic and transcendental incentives with the KM strategy; greater encouragement of knowledge-sharing attitudes; and more intensive use of technological tools.

Conclusions

Despite a high awareness (80.2%) of the importance of Knowledge Management (KM) in organizations, the results indicate that the degree of implementation of KM models is only 16%. Overall, these models are not utilized in Peruvian companies.

This study highlights that the main reasons for the low level of implementation of Knowledge Management (KM) models in the Peruvian industry are: 1) 84% of the sample is not familiar with KM models and concepts, which prevents them from developing these practices in their organizations. 2) 72.9% of respondents state that they do not have responsible roles for developing KM models and concepts within their organizations. 3) 53.5% of the sample indicates that KM is not part of the strategic plan.

Since the dimension with the lowest score is Indicators, it is likely that companies lack a measurement and control system for Knowledge Management (KM). As a result, the benefits of KM have not materialized. The danger lies in the possibility that these strategies could be abandoned due to the absence of indicators demonstrating value creation for the companies.

Lastly, regarding the limitations of this study, a convenience sample of employees from Peruvian companies was used in the methodology, which may not reflect the experiences of all organizations in the country. Additionally, sectoral differences were not explored in detail, which could be relevant for understanding how Knowledge Management (KM) varies across specific industries

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proposed to enhance the implementation and effectiveness of Knowledge Management (KM) in Peruvian companies

From a business perspective, companies could strengthen their Knowledge Management (KM) strategies by implementing the following action plans:

- Align Knowledge Management (KM) objectives with the company's strategic plan, ensuring that the organization's know-how serves this plan.
- Adopt a practical KM model that fits the needs and realities of the Peruvian industry.
- Designate specific roles for KM that facilitate implementation, continuous monitoring, and application of KM tools.
- Allocate the necessary budget for the implementation of KM.
- Establish a policy of extrinsic, intrinsic, and transcendental incentives that addresses human needs and motivates participation in KM strategies.

- Adopt collaborative technological platforms, networks, and knowledge communities that facilitate interaction and information exchange, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of internal communication, trust, and collaboration among employees.
- Establish a system for continuous monitoring and evaluation with operational and value indicators of the implemented KM practices, allowing for timely adjustments and ensuring the achievement of proposed objectives. A systematic evaluation will ensure the adaptation of KM strategies to the changing needs of the organization and the environment.

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